

HIPPARCOS

Some aspects on the elimination of rank deficiency

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INTRODUCTION

Both in the set solutions and in the PRS solution we are facing the computational difficulty that normal equations based purely on HIPPARCOS data are (or should be) singular: the rank deficiency should be one for a set solution (for the undefined abscissa zero point) and six for the PRS solution (three orientation angles and three components of the system rotation).

The problem can only be overcome by introducing external information. This can either be in the form of postulated properties of the resulting solution, or in the form of a priori (and inexact) data. From a computational point of view, the inclusion of postulated properties involves a constrained solution, while (inexact) a priori data can always be expressed as observation equations.

Apart from the generalized (pseudo-inverse) approach, which is not considered here, there are several ways in which a unique solution can be secured. We shall discuss the following four:

- (i) Using k linear constraints connecting many unknowns (k = rank deficiency). E.g., for the set solution it may be postulated that the sum of abscissa corrections should be zero.
- (ii) Using a priori values of many unknowns as additional low-weight 'observations'. E.g., FK5 positions and proper motions of PRS may be added to make the PRS solution definite.
- (iii) Postulating the values of k unknowns. (This is a special case of the constrained solution (i), with each constraint involving only one unknown.)
- (iv) Using the same linear equations as in (i), but regarding them not as rigorous constraints but as observation equations of finite weight.

(iii) was more or less the method used for the Copenhagen simulations of the spherical reconstitution (Hoyer et al., 1981). It is however the astrometrically least satisfactory one, especially for the PRS solution. Method (ii) has been mentioned as more satisfactory; but we shall see that it is computationally less favourable and also entails a risk that systematic errors of the a priori data are to some extent transferred to the solution. From a theoretical point of view (i) is definitely the preferred method; unfortunately the resulting system is not positive definite and therefore incompatible with the Cholesky algorithm. As a result of the present note it appears that (iv) is a suitable compromise, being both theoretically satisfactory and computationally convenient.

To gain some understanding of how the different methods work, let us consider a problem which is fundamentally similar to the set solution, but of such a simple structure that it is readily studied by analytical means.

AN ARCHETYPAL PROBLEM

Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ be a set of unknowns to be determined from relative measures only, i.e. from observation equations of the form $x_i - x_j = d_{ij}$, $i \neq j$. If all $n(n-1)/2$ possible distances are measured with the same accuracy corresponding to unit weight, the normal equations matrix, of dimension $n \times n$, will be

$$\underline{N}(n,n) = \begin{pmatrix} n-1 & -1 & -1 & \dots & -1 \\ -1 & n-1 & -1 & \dots & -1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & \dots & n-1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

which is obviously singular, since the sum of each row is zero. If $\underline{I}(n,n)$ is the identity matrix of order n and $\underline{U}(m,n)$ denotes an m -by- n matrix of ones, we write more concisely

$$\underline{N}(n,n) = n \underline{I}(n,n) - \underline{U}(n,n). \quad (2)$$

Introducing the n -vector of ones, $\underline{u}(n) = (1 \ 1 \ 1 \ \dots \ 1)'$, we have $\underline{U}(n,n) \underline{u}(n) = n \underline{u}(n)$; hence

$$\underline{N}(n,n) \underline{u}(n) = 0 \underline{u}(n). \quad (3)$$

That is, $\underline{u}(n)$ is an eigenvector of $\underline{N}(n,n)$ with eigenvalue $\lambda_1 = 0$. To obtain the other eigenvalues we define $n-1$ linearly independent n -vectors

$$\underline{v}_i(n) = (1 \ 0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0 \ \underset{\substack{\uparrow \\ i:\text{th element}}}{-1} \ 0 \ \dots \ 0)'$$
, $i = 2, 3, \dots, n. \quad (4)$

Since $\underline{U}(m,n) \underline{v}_i(n) = \underline{0}(m)$ (the null vector of length m), we find

$$\underline{N}(n,n) \underline{v}_i(n) = n \underline{I}(n,n) \underline{v}_i(n) - \underline{U}(n,n) \underline{v}_i(n) = n \underline{v}_i(n). \quad (5)$$

$\underline{v}_i(n)$ are therefore eigenvectors with eigenvalues $\lambda_i = n$, $i = 2, 3, \dots, n$.

The rank deficiency, i.e. the multiplicity of eigenvalue zero, is $k = 1$.

We define the condition number of an n -by- n matrix as the ratio of the numerically largest eigenvalue to the numerically smallest, i.e.

$$C = \max(|\lambda_1|, |\lambda_2|, \dots, |\lambda_n|) / \min(|\lambda_1|, |\lambda_2|, \dots, |\lambda_n|). \quad (6)$$

For $\underline{N}(n,n)$ we have of course $C = \infty$. We shall see how the various methods mentioned in the Introduction alter the structure of the normal equations, and especially their effects on C and the inverse matrix.

(i) Constrained solution

Let $\hat{x}_i$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ be a priori values of the unknowns, all being equally uncertain. A suitable linear constraint, which would cause the zero-point of the solution to agree in a least-squares sense with the a priori data, is

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a x_i = \sum_{i=1}^n a \hat{x}_i, \quad (7)$$

where a is any non-zero constant. The normal equation matrix augmented by the constraint and the coefficients of the Lagrangian multiplier, is then

$$\underline{N}_{(i)} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{N}(n,n) & a \underline{u}(n) \\ a \underline{u}(n)' & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

the inverse of which is

$$\underline{N}_{(i)}^{-1} = n^{-2} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{N}(n,n) & \frac{n}{a} \underline{u}(n) \\ \frac{n}{a} \underline{u}(n)' & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$\underline{v}_i(n+1)$, $i = 2, 3, \dots, n$ are eigenvectors with eigenvalues $\lambda_i = n$; the remaining two eigenvalues are an^2 and $-an^2$, e.g. for eigenvectors $(1 \ 1 \ \dots \ 1 \ \pm n^{\frac{1}{2}})'$. The condition number is

$$C_{(i)} = \max(a/n^{\frac{1}{2}}, n^{\frac{1}{2}}/a). \quad (10)$$

Since the number a can be chosen at will, we get $C = 1$ with $a = n^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

It should be noted that the upper-left part of the inverse matrix, $n^{-2}\underline{N}(n,n)$, is independent of the number a and can be regarded as the covariance of the solution. It is in fact the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of $\underline{N}(n,n)$.

Important is also that the augmented matrix (8) has one negative eigenvalue; it is therefore indefinite and the constrained least-squares problem cannot be solved by the (real) Cholesky method.

(ii) A priori data as additional observations

If the a priori values $\hat{x}_i$ are given a certain weight $w \ll 1$, they can be introduced into the least-squares problem in the form of observation equations of unit weight,

$$w^{\frac{1}{2}} x_i = w^{\frac{1}{2}} \hat{x}_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (11)$$

The modified normal equations matrix is

$$\underline{N}_{(ii)} = \underline{N}(n,n) + w \underline{I}(n,n) = (n+w) \underline{I}(n,n) - \underline{U}(n,n). \quad (12)$$

The inverse matrix is

$$\underline{N}_{(ii)}^{-1} = [w(n+w)]^{-1} [w \underline{I}(n,n) + \underline{U}(n,n)]. \quad (13)$$

Compared with the 'true' variance of the unknown, $(n-1)/n^2$ from (9), the variance is overestimated roughly by a factor $1/w$. In addition, the correlation between the unknowns is very strong, $1/(1+w)$.

It is seen that $\underline{u}(n)$ and $\underline{v}_i(n)$ are still eigenvectors, as for $\underline{N}(n,n)$; but the eigenvalues are $\lambda_1 = w$, $\lambda_i = n+w$, $i = 2, 3, \dots, n$. The condition number is therefore

$$C_{(ii)} = 1 + n/w. \quad (14)$$

The errors of $\hat{x}_i$ are to some extent transferred to the solution (roughly by a fraction w , possibly more for errors of a 'systematic' nature). Thus, it is necessary to take w sufficiently small, perhaps 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} in practical cases. The condition number is then of the order of 10^7 or more.

(iii) Postulated unknown

If e.g. the solution $x_n = \hat{x}_n$ is postulated for the last unknown, the effect on the normal equations is simply to delete the last row and last column. The modified matrix is

$$\underline{N}_{(iii)} = \underline{N}(n-1, n-1) + \underline{I}(n-1, n-1), \quad (15)$$

which is identical to (12) with $w := 1$ and $n := n-1$. From (13) we have then

$$\underline{N}_{(iii)}^{-1} = n^{-1} \underline{I}(n-1, n-1) + \underline{U}(n-1, n-1). \quad (16)$$

The condition number is, from (14),

$$C_{(iii)} = n. \quad (16)$$

(iv) Treating the constraint as an observation

If (7) is regarded as an observation equation of unit weight, one obtains the modified normal equations matrix

$$\underline{N}_{(iv)} = \underline{N}(n, n) + a^2 \underline{U}(n, n) = n \underline{I}(n, n) + (a^2 - 1) \underline{U}(n, n). \quad (17)$$

$\underline{v}_i(n)$ are still eigenvectors with eigenvalues $\lambda_i = n$ for $i = 2, 3, \dots, n$.

Moreover,

$$\underline{N}_{(iv)} \underline{u}(n) = n \underline{I}(n, n) \underline{u}(n) + (a^2 - 1) \underline{U}(n, n) \underline{u}(n) = a^2 n \underline{u}(n); \quad (18)$$

so $\underline{u}(n)$ is an eigenvector with eigenvalue $\lambda_1 = na^2$. The condition number is

$$C_{(iv)} = \max(a^2, a^{-2}). \quad (19)$$

By choosing $a = 1$, the condition number becomes $C = 1$ and $\underline{N}_{(iv)}$ is diagonal.

The inverse matrix is

$$\underline{N}_{(iv)}^{-1} = (an)^{-2} [na^2 \underline{I}(n, n) - (a^2 - 1) \underline{U}(n, n)]. \quad (20)$$

Discussion

From the above results we conclude:

- that method (i), although in theory the best method, must be rejected because of the indefinite matrix;
- that (ii) is unsuitable both because of the danger of bias propagation and the very high condition number;
- that (iii) is much better from the numerical point of view, but astrometrically unsatisfactory;
- that (iv) is well conditioned, positive definite, and astrometrically satisfactory; moreover, the estimated variances from the inverse matrix are correct to the first order in $1/n$.

Thus it seems clear that (iv) is the preferred method.

There is a snag however. In reality the singular matrix corresponding to $\underline{N}(n,n)$ is only partially filled, i.e. a large fraction of the off-diagonal elements are zero (which greatly reduces the amount of computation when solving the system). If an equation involving practically all the unknowns, like (7), is added as an observation, the result will be a nearly full matrix.

As an attempt to reduce this problem we consider finally the case when only a subset of the unknowns, say the first m unknowns, are included in the constraint.

(v) Partial constraint treated as an observation

Let the partial constraint be

$$\sum_{i=1}^m a x_i = \sum_{i=1}^m a \hat{x}_i, \quad m < n. \quad (21)$$

The modified normal equations matrix is

$$\underline{N}_{(v)} = \underline{N}(n,n) + \begin{pmatrix} a^2 \underline{U}(m,m) & \underline{0}(m,n-m) \\ \underline{0}(n-m,m) & \underline{0}(n-m,n-m) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

$\underline{v}_i(n)$, $i = 2, 3, \dots, m$ and $\underline{v}_i(n) - \underline{v}_{m+1}(n)$, $i = m+2, m+3, \dots, n$ are $n-2$ eigenvectors with eigenvalue n . The remaining two eigenvectors are e.g. of the form $(z \ z \ \dots \ z \ 1 \ 1 \ \dots \ 1)'$, where $z = 1 - \lambda/m$ and

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{2} [ma^2 + n \pm \{(ma^2 + n)^2 - 4m^2 a^2\}^{\frac{1}{2}}]. \quad (23)$$

The condition number has a minimum for $a^2 \approx n/m$, for which $\lambda = n \pm [n(n-m)]^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and

$$C_{(v)} = \frac{2}{m} [n + \{n(n-m)\}^{\frac{1}{2}}] - 1. \quad (24)$$

For $m \ll n$ we have $C \approx 4n/m$.

The inverse matrix is, for $a^2 = n/m$,

$$\underline{N}_{(v)}^{-1} = \frac{1}{n} \underline{I}(n,n) + \frac{1}{mn} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{0}(m,m) & \underline{U}(m,n-m) \\ \underline{U}(n-m,m) & 2 \underline{U}(n-m,n-m) \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

Thus, the relative error of the variance as obtained from (25) is about $2/m$, which may be acceptable for $m \gtrsim 20$. With $n \sim 1000$ we have then $C \lesssim 200$. The fill-in factor is of the order of m/n or $(m/n)^2$ (depending on how it is defined); in any case it appears that a satisfactory compromise can be reached with proper choice of m .